

Australian Government

Department of Defence

Defence Science and Technology Group

Designing Novel Composite Structural Supercapacitors with Discrete Carbon Nanotube Electrodes

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PUBLIC RELEASE

Composite Structural Supercapacitors (SSCs)

- Improvement in Size, Weight, and Power (SWaP) energy storage to mobile devices or transportation vehicles
- Electrode and electrolyte materials have been well developed for SSCs
- However, little work has focused on developing materials for the SSC separator layer
 - Common materials: cellulose filter paper, glass fibre fabric, aramid fibre fabrics, porous polymer membranes
- Non-conductive porous materials such as boron nitride nanotubes (BNNTs) can be incorporated to one surface of the electrode material, removing the need for the separator layer altogether

Boron Nitride Nanotubes (BNNTs)

- Strong, light weight and chemically resilient
- Thin film materials that possess high structural integrity and porosity
- Dimensionally stable and capable of withstanding high temperature
- High potential for high-power composite structural supercapacitors applications

This work combines commercially available carbon nanotube (CNT) mat with BNNTs coating to produce a high-performance fibre-reinforced polymer composite using industrial autoclave curing techniques.

BNNTs Coating Method

Stable dispersed mixture of BNNTs, achieved using sonicated ozonolysis. Sonication reduces the size of large BNNT agglomerates and cleaves BNNTs to decrease their average length.

Oxygen-functionalised CNT Mats, treated for 6h prior to BNNT coating. This process enhances the water permeability for better vacuum filtration.

Porous support underneath CNT Mat can be tailored using a glass fibre filter paper to control coating homogeneity.

CNT-BNNT self standing electrode and separator

Dried CNT-BNNT film. Polymeric binder can also be combined in the BNNT suspension before vacuum filtration for more uniform coating.

Coating Characterisation

- Four different binders were used: PEG, PVP, PEI, PBBDT
- Addition of PEG, PVP and PBBDT has significantly improved coverage of CNT mat creases
- Some agglomerates (white spots) can form during deposition due to dispersion instability
- Addition of polymeric binders leads to micro-scale network
- BNNT-PBBDT coating demonstrated the best overall characteristics, with homogeneous coverage and limited agglomerate formation

Coating Electrochemical Performance

- 2016 Coin cell with CNT-BNNT as electrodes
- EMIM TFSI ionic liquid as the electrolyte
- BNNT-PBDT
 - Best performance at low cycling rates
 - Excellent capacity retention
 - Coulombic efficiency above 98%
- BNNT-PVP and BNNT-PEI: deterioration and loss in capacitance after 2,000 cycles

BNNT-PBDT Electrochemical Performance

- Best microstructure and all round electrochemical performance with EMIM TFSI electrolyte
- Stable operation up to 4V
- Pyrrolidinium electrolytes have higher specific energies at low charge-discharge rate, but worse performance at higher cycling rate, which decreases further with extended cycling.
- Alternative polymer systems required to improve the performance of the pyrrolidinium electrolytes

Composite SSC using CNT-BNNT

- Manufactured using industry standard vacuum-bag and autoclave-cure techniques
- Composite device demonstrated better performance than the coin cell, with 12.8 Wh.kg^{-1} at $0.0984 \text{ kW.kg}^{-1}$
- Good capacitance observed from CV curve
- High coulombic efficiency maintained after extended cycling (above 94%)
- Highly suitable for integration into composite structures

Conclusions

- CNT-BNNT coatings were produced using four different polymeric binders: PEG, PVP, PEI, PBDT
- Coin-cell testings demonstrated good performance with selected binders
 - PBDT showed the best overall electrochemical results
 - High specific energy up to 15.2 Wh.kg^{-1}
- Composite structural supercapacitor performance exceeded the coin cell performance
- Strong viability of CNT-BNNT coatings for integration into large-scale composite structures

Acknowledgements

- storEnergy – The ARC Training Centre for Future Energy Storage Technologies
- Deakin University
- Dr Vu Dao, Defence Science and Technology Group

